

Economy of different rice-based cropping patterns for Cauvery Delta

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Eight rice-based cropping patterns for the Cauvery Delta were studied for profitability in 1981-82 at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai. Soil at the experimental site was clay loam with low available N, medium available P, and high available K, with pH 7.5. Rice and summer crop yields were assessed individually and the gross margin was calculated for the pattern, by subtracting

Gross margins of different rice-based cropping patterns, Aduthurai, India 1981-82.

Cropping pattern ^a			Gross margin (\$/ha)
Kuruvai (Jul-Oct)	Thaladi (Oct-Feb)	Summer (Feb-Jun)	
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Cotton (MCU 7) + blackgram	887
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Sorghum + cowpea	527
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Maize + soybean	473
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Sunflower + cowpea	302
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Greengram	482
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Cotton (MCU 7)	961
Rice (TKM 9)	Rice (IR20)	Bhendi (Co. 1)	786
Rice (CR 1009)	Rice (AD103)	Pearl millet (Co. 6)	159
	CD (P = 0.05)		

^aReplicated 3 times.

the cost of cultivation from the gross income for each pattern.

Annual gross margin was \$961/ha for

rice - rice - cotton + blackgram, \$887/ha for rice - rice - cotton, and \$786/ha for rice - rice - bhendi (see table). □

Announcements

IR58, IR60 released in the Philippines

The Philippine Seed Board has named two new IRRI-developed rice varieties, IR58 and IR60, for release in the Philippines.

IR58 is the line IR9752-71-3-2, developed from the progeny of the cross IR28/Kwang Chang Ai//IR36. IR58 matures in 100 days, has high levels of tungro and blast disease resistance, resists brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2, and has cooking quality similar to that of IR36. It was recommended for cultivation in Luzon and Visayas.

IR60 is the line IR13429-299-2-1-3-1, selected from the progeny of the cross IR4432-53-33/PTB33//IR36. It has been recommended for cultivation in Mindanao because it resists brown planthopper biotypes 1, 2, and 3. IR60 matures in 105 days, It has long slender grains and a high level of blast resistance.

Release of the two varieties brings the number of IR varieties released in the Philippines to 26. The first 11 varieties were named by IRRI. Beginning with IR36, released in 1976, all IR varieties released in the Philippines have been named by the Philippine Seed Board. □

Rice germplasm conservation workshop

A 2-day workshop on the conservation of rice germplasm was co-sponsored by IRRI and International Board for Plant Germplasm Resources 25-26 April. Thirty-five scientists from 21 countries, 9 staff members from 6 other international agricultural research centers and international agencies, and IRRI staff participated in the conference.

Progress in field collection from 1977 to 1982 was reviewed and papers on conservation methodology, the wild *Oryza* species, and seed storage equipment for national centers were presented to assist the germplasm workers. Inter-institutional collaboration between the United States Department of Agriculture, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, and IRRI was reassessed.

The following areas were identified as priority efforts: urgency in completing the collection of land races, conservation of wild species, systematic evaluation and characterization, seed storage (primarily medium-term), documentation at national centers, manpower development, security of seedstocks under long-term storage, and free germplasm exchange.

Participants from South Asia, Southeast Asia, and Africa drafted a 5-year collection plan and estimated funding requirements. IRRI will continue to coordinate field operations and provide an adviser or field collector. Small-scale collection in Latin America and Oceania will be separately developed.

The scope of the Advisory Committee to the International Rice Germplasm Center at IRRI was also discussed. The Center was recently reorganized to increase security to the rice germplasm bank, and is now a component of IRRI's Global Research Services. □

IRRI-TARC seminar

IRRI and the Tropical Agriculture Research Center of Japan sponsored a seminar on *Collection and utilization of genetic resources in rice with particular reference to disease resistance* 6 Apr 1983, at Tsukuba Science City.

The conference was the third in a series of cooperative meetings to stimulate interest of Japanese scientists in tropical rice and rice-based cropping systems.